

Synthesis of some 1,2-Bis(styrylsulphonylmethyl)benzenes

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The important properties of sulphones have culminated in the synthesis and structural studies of a vast number of compounds incorporating such a moiety¹. The sulphones have also acquired importance chemotherapeutically as this moiety is found to be a potential pharmacophore in many carbocyclic and heterocyclic systems^{2,3}. In view of the above observations and as a part of our general program in the continued search for new organosulphur compounds, synthesis of some new 1,2-bis(styrylsulphonylmethyl)benzenes have been undertaken.

Photochemical bromination of 1,2-dimethylbenzene (1) gave 1,2-bis(bromomethyl)benzene (2). The nucleophilic displacement of bromine in 2 by the sodium salt of mercaptoacetic acid (3) afforded 1,2-xylylenedithioacetic acid (4) which on oxidation resulted the corresponding xylylenedisulphonyl acetic acid (5). Knoevenagel condensation of 5 with the araldehydes (6) in the presence of catalytic amount of benzylamine yielded 1,2-bis(styrylsulphonylmethyl)benzenes (7) (Scheme 1).

The uv spectra of 7 exhibited two bands at 264–292 and 204–242 nm. The high intensity band is due to the conjugation of sulphur atom with styryl moiety⁴. The ϵ -band of benzene which occurs at 180 nm, presumably appeared as a second band as a result of bathochromic shift. The methyl, methoxyethoxy, halogen and nitro substituents in the *para*-positions of the phenyl moiety causes a bathochromic shift in their λ_{\max}

7; Ar = a; C₆H₅, b; 4-CH₃C₆H₄, c; 4-FC₆H₄, d; 2-ClC₆H₄, e; 4-ClC₆H₄, f; 4-BrC₆H₄, g; 2-NO₂C₆H₄, h; 4-NO₂C₆H₄, i; 3-OCH₃-4-OC₂H₅C₆H₃, j; 2,4-Cl₂C₆H₃

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) Br₂/hv, (ii) NaOH/MeOH, (iii) H₂O₂/AcOH and (iv) C₆H₅CH₂NH₂/AcOH.

along with hyperchromic effect in ϵ_{\max} . However, these effects are relatively less when the same substituents are in *ortho*-position. The ir spectra of 7 exhibited⁵ bands at 1 625–1 610 (C=C), 1 000–970 (CH out-of-plane) and 1 340–1 310 and 1 152–1 120 cm⁻¹ (SO₂). Its ¹H nmr spectra showed signals at δ 6.80–7.00 and 7.40–7.90 as doublets for the ethylenic protons H_A and H_B. In some instances the signals of H_B are superimposed with aromatic signals and appeared as multiplets⁶. The J_{AB} values have been found to be 16.0–16.4 Hz confirming the *E,E*-geometry of these compounds. The methylene protons showed δ_H values at 4.60–4.80, while the aromatic ring protons at δ 7.10–7.40 as multiplets. The ¹³C nmr spectra exhibited δ_C values for ethylenic carbons C-8 and C-8' and C-9 and C-9' in the region 141.1–146.2 and 130.9–138.3 ppm respectively. The C-8 and C-8', as a result of strong

deshielding effect of sulphone moiety, appeared at downfield region than C-9 and C-9'⁷. The methylene carbon appeared at 58.4–61.5 ppm. The mass spectrum of **7** showed low intense molecular ion-peak at m/z 436, in agreement with its chemical composition $C_{24}H_{22}S_2O_4$. A facile extrusion of SO_2 and SO_2H^* , the scission of C–O bond in sulphonyl-sulphinat rearrangement and McLafferty type rearrangement are found to be dominant features in the degradation of the molecular ion of these compounds⁸. The important daughter ions formed lend support to the structures of these compounds.

Experimental

The melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) at 250 MHz on a GE NMR Omega spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Finnigan Mat 1210 spectrometer at 70 eV. The purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography. All the compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

1,2-Bis(bromomethyl)benzene (2) : A solution of 1,2-dimethylbenzene (106 g, 1 mol) was heated to 125° in an oil-bath with vigorous stirring. The solution was illuminated with 500 W power lamp and bromine (2.2 mol, 352 g) was added slowly over a period of 90–120 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured in boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), cooled and refrigerated overnight. The solid separated was washed with petroleum ether (2 × 20 ml) and dried. The resulting brown crystalline compound (135 g, 51%), m.p. 89–90° (lit.⁹ 89–94°) was kept in a vacuum desiccator.

1,2-Xylylenedisulphonylacetic acid (5) : To a solution of NaOH (40 g, 1 mol) in methanol (600 ml), mercaptoacetic acid (46 g, 0.5 mol) was added slowly. Then **2** (0.5 mol) was added in portions and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The cooled contents were poured onto crushed ice and neutralised with dilute HCl (400 ml).

The resulting solid was washed, dried and recrystallised from hot water to give **4** (78%, m.p. 85–86°). Compound **4** (0.8 mol) was oxidised by refluxing with 30% hydrogen peroxide (1.92 mol) in glacial acetic acid (225 ml) for 1–2 h. The contents were cooled and acetic acid was removed under vacuum. The dense liquid which separated was then poured onto crushed ice and the solid obtained was crystallised from hot water to yield **5** (71% m.p. 199–200°).

1,2-Bis(styrylsulphonylmethyl)benzene (7a-j) : A solution of **5** (0.1 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was treated with araldehyde (0.2 mol) in presence of a catalytic amount of benzylamine. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 1.5–2 h, cooled, treated with dry ether (50 ml) and refrigerated overnight. The solid separated was collected and the filtrate was diluted with more ether. In some instances a solid product was obtained immediately upon cooling or upon addition of ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with a saturated solution of aqueous sodium carbonate (15 ml), aqueous sodium bisulphite (15 ml), dilute HCl (20 ml) and finally with water. Evaporation of the dried ethereal layer yielded a solid residue. The combined solid thus obtained was crystallised either from ethanol or from acetic acid to give **7a** (61%), m.p. 141–42°; λ_{max} 216 (ϵ 5 140), 268 (6 795); ν_{max} 1 620 (C=C), 1 300, 1 140 (SO_2), 975 cm^{-1} (CH out-of-plane), δ_H 4.73 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.90 (2H, d, H_A), 7.47 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.3 Hz), 7.31–7.43 (14H, m, ArH); δ_C 58.40 (C-7, C-7'), 133.28 (C-9, C-9'), 145.34 (C-8, C-8'); m/z (rel. int.) 271 (13), 213 (17), 207 (10), 183 (47), 167 (4), 155 (7), 119 (48), 105 (12), 100 (40), 103 (37), 102 (13), 92 (13), 91 (100), 78 (27), 77 (35); **b** (71%), m.p. 169–70° λ_{max} 242 (ϵ 4 245), 275 (6 380); ν_{max} 1 625, 1 315, 1 130, 970 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 2.73 (6H, s, CH_3), 4.72 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.77 (2H, d, J_{AB} 16.3 Hz), 7.10–7.36 (12H, m, ArH); δ_C 21.48 (C- CH_3), 58.79 (C-7, C-7'), 133.44 (2C, C-8, C-8') 145.63 (2C, C-9, C-9'); **c** (74%), m.p. 209–10°; λ_{max} 236 (ϵ 890), 270 (2 730); ν_{max} 1 622, 1 335, 1 150, 985 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.68 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.86 (2H, d, H_A), 7.54 (2H, d,

H_B , J_{AB} 16.2 Hz), 7.26–7.48 (12H, d, ArH); δ_C 58.68 (2C, C-7, C-7'), 132.78 (2C, C-8, C-8'), 143.89 (2C, C-9, C-9'); **d** (82%), m.p. 232–33°; ν_{max} 1 610, 1 320, 1 120, 970 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.65 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.82 (2H, d, H_A), 7.46 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.4 Hz), 7.18–7.40 (12H, m, ArH); δ_C 58.82 (2C, C-7, C-7'), 133.94 (2C, C-8, C-8'), 144.12 (2C, C-9, C-9'); **e** (76%), m.p. 193–94°; λ_{max} 228 (ϵ 1 085), 270 (2 960); ν_{max} 1 615, 1 325, 1 120, 975 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.70 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.80 (2H, d, H_A), 7.49 (2H, d, H_B , J 16.2 Hz), 7.35–7.40 (12H, m, ArH); **f** (87%), m.p. 212–14°; λ_{max} 226 (ϵ 1 220), 276 nm (4 170); ν_{max} 1 620, 1 340, 1 150, 980 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.70 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.81 (2H, d, H_A), 7.47 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.2 Hz), 7.26–7.48 (12H, m, ArH); δ_C 58.94 (2C, C-7, C-7'), 133.64 (2C, C-8, C-8'), 144.42 (2C, C-9, C-9'); **g** (72%), m.p. 203–04°; λ_{max} 204 (ϵ 4 780), 272 (4 265); ν_{max} 1 625, 1 330, 1 145, 990 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.76 (4H, s, CH_2), 7.38 (2H, d, H_A), 8.05 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.0 Hz), 7.50–7.86 (12H, m, ArH); **h** (84%), m.p. 249–50°; λ_{max} 210 (ϵ 5 040), 280 nm (4 625); ν_{max} 1 615, 1 340, 1 120, 985 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.82 (4H, s, CH_2), 7.43 (2H, d, H_A), 8.27 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.4 Hz), 7.58–7.98 (12H, m, ArH); δ_C 58.86 (2C, C-7, C-7'), 133.24 (2C, C-8, C-8'), 141.12 (2C, C-9, C-9'); **i** (66%), m.p. 225–26°; λ_{max} 242 (5 590), 2 92 (2 750), 322 nm (3 660); ν_{max}

1 622, 1 330 1 130, 975 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 1.42 (6H, t, CH_3), 3.92 (6H, s, CH_3O), 4.02 (4H, q, CH_2), 4.65 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.85 (2H, d, H_A), 7.50 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.0 Hz), 7.28–7.44 (10H, m, ArH); **j** (85%), m.p. 209–10°; λ_{max} 239 (ϵ 1 695), 278 nm (4 970); ν_{max} 1620, 1 335, 1 125, 980 cm^{-1} ; δ_H 4.68 (4H, s, CH_2), 6.88 (2H, d, H_A), 7.52 (2H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 16.4 Hz), 7.20–7.42 (10H, m, ArH); δ_C 58.90 (2C, C-7, C-7'), 132.96 (2C, C-8, C-8'), 144.56 (2C, C-9, C-9').

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